

Impact of Artificial Intelligence Applications on Profitability of Large-Scale Retailers in Gweru Urban, Zimbabwe

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Abstract:

The study focused on the impact of artificial intelligence on the profitability of large-scale retailers in Gweru urban Zimbabwe. The study revealed that most of the successful retailers across the world are as a result of adopting artificial intelligence. In Gweru urban there is less utilisation of artificial intelligence by large scale-retailers. The study revealed a number of factors promoting the adoption of artificial intelligence by large-scale retailers. These factors include, technological readiness, availability of big data, organisational culture, regulatory framework, taxpayer acceptance, the need for data quality and privacy and security concerns. Also, the study Analysed the artificial intelligence applications for large-scale retailers. These AI include, price optimisation, fraud detection and prevention,

predictive analytics for more accurate sales forecasting, supply chain optimisation, customer service Chatbots and automated replies, inventory management, personalised recommendations, visual search and image recognition. The study also, examined the impact of artificial intelligence on the operations of large-scale retailers. The impact of AI discussed include; improved accuracy, enhanced fraud detection, increased efficiency, real time monitoring, data driven policy making, improved customer experience, cost driven savings, revenue growth, provide a source of competitive advantage. The study revealed the challenges of adopting AI these include; data quality issues, lack of transparency and accountability. The study adopted a pragmatism philosophy as it utilised both qualitative and quantitative strategies in collecting and analysed the data. The results of the study revealed that there is a positive significance in adopting and implementing artificial intelligence on the profitability large-scale retailers.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Applications, Profitability, Large-Scale Retailers, Zimbabwe.*

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Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly reshaping the global and the national retail sector. The astronomic rise of electronic commerce and the omnichannel retail through data gathering and analysis are bringing significant disruption to the retail sector (Hofmann,2021). The world retailers contribute an average 32% of the world Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Syan & Sharma, 2021). In most European economies, retail trade employ 27,5 million workers across the European countries in 2023 (Yang, 2020). In Zimbabwe by the year 2022 a report by the Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency (ZIMSTAT, 2023), there were approximately 12, 444 retail establishment in Zimbabwe. In the year 2023 the report by the Confederation of Zimbabwe Retailers (CZR, 2023) estimated that there were around 15 000 retail outlets in Zimbabwe. The major challenges of the retail shops in the global South are the low level of the adoption and implementation of artificial intelligence than their counterparts in the global North (Jiang & Ren, 2019). The substantial increase in labour increase in labour productivity from 2014 to 2023 as the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) boosted by the artificial intelligence (Alessandro & Guariso, 2020).

Advances in artificial intelligence, computer processing and the availability of big data are significant in increasing wide range of retailers to automate many retail tasks ranging from warehouse robots and customer service chatbots to enable fast and efficient way of conducting retail businesses (Anica-Popa, Anica-Popa, Raduscu Vrincianu, 2021). Artificial Intelligence (AI) continues to leave its mark in the retail industry. In retail stores artificial intelligence is making big waves and it is changing every retail industry experiences. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is revolutionising the retail industry in numerous ways such as providing many opportunities to enhance potential customer experience, drive sales and optimising sales and optimize retail operations as well as enabling the easy

computation of taxation (Barnes & Owens, 2019).

Most of the world largest retailers are found in the global North. The most reasons for the success of the world's largest retailers are as a result of their huge investments in artificial intelligence. Examples of the most successful large retailers include; Walmart (USA), Carrefour (France), Tesco (UK), Aidi (Germany), AIDI (Germany), IKEA (Sweden), Costco (USA), Home Depot (USA), Amazon (USA), Aliba Group (China) These retailers are thriving as a result of fully utilising artificial intelligence in their retail operations (Birdi & Spencer, 2019). Also, table 1 shows the top ten performing large-scale retailers in the world by 2023. The success of these large-scale retailers of the world is as a result of adopting and implementing high level of technology.

In Zimbabwe a number of successful retailers such as Pick n Pay, OK Bazaars and many others are adopting the services of AI such as online sales, online advertisement. Many large-scale retailers in Zimbabwe recently introduced online service known as click and collect in which both local and international buyers are able to pay online and collect their products from any branch of the specified retail outlet in the country (Bostrom, 2021). In addition to that, large-scale retailers are now conducting online purchase by placing an order online, paying for the order online receive online receipts and goods are delivered at their door step at their convenience Bradlow, (Gangwar, Kopalle, and Voleti, 2020).

Large-scale retail companies specialise in selling of goods and or services to consumers at both local and international markets. The products that are commonly sold by large-scale retailers include; groceries, housewares, jewellery, electronics, pharmaceutical product and small appliances (Carson, 2019). The services that are provided by large-scale-retailers include auto care, pharmacies, rentals, cloud computing, money transfers, tool and equipment. In the United States of America (USA) retail spending is one of the most consumer spending and

accounts for two thirds of the its economic activity (Chou, Chuang, & Shao, 2019).

The contemporary retailers are selling their goods and services through online using their websites, marketplaces, internet and various applications of mobile applications. unlike traditional retailers who operated through brick-and- mortar store (Dixon et al, 2019). The ten biggest retail companies are engaging in both

retail and wholesale business, they do sell an assortment of merchandise and services worldwide at stores and online at everyday low prices Dourado, & Pestana, (2020). Retail shops like Walmart (USA), Amazon (USA). Com Inc, Costco (USA) Wholesale Corp (South Africa), the Home Depot Inc (USA), JD. Com Inc. (China, Indonesia, Thailand) and many others utilise fully the available technology for boosting their business operations.

Table 1. Shows the Performance of the World's Top Ten Biggest Retail Companies Who Adopt AI

Name of Retail Company	Revenue US\$\$ Billion	Net Income US\$\$ Billion	Market Cap US\$\$ Billion	1-Year Trailing	Exchange
Walmart	600.1 billion	9.0 billion	391.5 billion	5.6%	New York Stock Exchange
Amazon.Com	502.2	11.3	885.2	- 49.1%	Nasdaq
Costco Wholesale Cor	231.0	5.9	205.1	-14.7%	Nasdaq
The Home Depot	157.3	17.1	325.5	-16.2%	NYSE
JD. Com Inc	156.9	254.3	91.0	-18.9%	Nasdaq
The Kroger Co	146.5	2.4	31.8	3.3%	NYSE
Walgreens Boots Alliance	132.7	4.3	33.4	-19.1%	Nasdaq
Alibaba Holdings	131.4	2.3	232.5	-28.6%	Nasdaq
Target Corp	108.7	3.5%	65.5	-34.0%	NYSE
Lowe's Companies	96.0	6.7%	122.4	-16.5%	NYSE

Source: Based Johnston Matthew Report, 2023

Table 1 shows ten large- scale retail performing companies of the world. The information on table 1 is based on the large-scale retail companies that are trading at the United States of America stock exchange by 2023. The success of the large-scale retailers is a result of adopting and implementing artificial intelligence in their business operations (Matthew, 2023).

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the development of computer systems that can perform tasks that typically imitate human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, problem solving, perception, language understanding and many others (World Economic Forum, 2020). AI systems use algorithms and data to make decisions, often without human intervention. There are various types of Artificial Intelligence that are available for large-scale retailers, these include; narrow or weak AI, general or strong

AI, superintelligence and many others (Poole, Mackworth & Goebel, 2021).

Profitability refers to the net profit earned by the business after deducting total operating expenses. It is the gain attained by the business organisations in its operating activities. Profitability is the most important measure of business operations David, (2019). Profitability constitutes the degree of going concern of the business. High profitability means the going concern of the business is health (Crawford, 2019). Whereas, the low profitability of the business means that the going concern of the business is at threat.

Automation refers to the use of technology to perform tasks without human intervention, using programmed instructions or algorithms to control and operate machines, processes, or systems (Chou, Chuang, 2019). The main

purpose of automation is to increase efficiency, while reducing human error and labour costs (Legg &Hutter, 2020). There are many types of automation that are available for large-scale retailers, these include; fixed automation, programmable automation, flexible automation, integrated automation and many others (Bostrom, 2021).

The advent of Artificial Intelligent (AI) and Automation are deeply impacting on the modern structure of the value chain transforming the ownership-based industrial society into service driven information society. The contemporary economy, technologies are increasingly widespread and pervasive (Dwork, 2019). There are new forms of generating value which can be moved from one place to another with great speed and easy as well as giving value to new markets (Feng, & Fay, 2020). The use of digital networks, whose economic potentialities are not limited by national boundaries but have changed the market, which is no longer a physical place for exchanging of goods, rather there is effective interconnected, easy-to access, open space without borders where to freely exchange data, goods, and temporary use rights (Webster, 2022).

Modern business environment is characterised by the synergies between data and data processing technologies, which allow supply of new digital services. The existence of big data flows enabled the increased number of computer-mediated transactions. Big data have been integrated into a global interconnected data processing infrastructure centred on internet. The presence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) enables businesses to conduct their shopping using banking and other financial services, pay taxes, get government benefits and other business services (Dixon et al, (2019).

The contemporary digital economy is characterised by the increased use of robotics. These robotics are simply defined as, “Artificial Intelligent (AI) in action in the physical world” (embodied AI). Precisely, a robot is the physical machine that has to cope-up with the dynamics, the uncertainties and the complexity of the physical world. Artificial intelligent (AI) is

changing the production process and supply of goods and services as well the buying and selling of goods and services. Retail robots would be feasible even if there is no legal personality Barnes, & Owens, (2019). This can be attained through object retail for example, the payment of a transaction. Retail could be based on fixed or flexible rates depending on the type of AI.

Purpose and Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to explore the impact of artificial intelligent applications on the profitability of large-scale retailers in Gweru urban - Zimbabwe.

The Specific Objectives of the Study are to:

- Establish factors promoting the adoption of artificial intelligence for automation in large-scale retailers.
- Analysing the artificial intelligence applications for large-scale retailers.
- Examine the impact of artificial intelligence on the operations of large-scale retailers.

Literature Review

The related literature for the study focused on the theoretical framework guiding the study and followed by the answering of the research objectives of the study.

Theoretical Framework

The study is guided by “The New Retail Wheel” Theory propounded by Masao Nakanishi a Japanese scholar. Masao Nakanishi combines the development trend of the retail industry at that time IEEE, (2020). He believed that, technology drives the retail industry to change its everyday business. He further put forward a new concept of “Technology boundary line”. Masao Nakanishi proposed that, retail enterprise can win the competition in the retail market only by carrying out technological innovation and making the technological boundary line move. Jiang Yaping & Ren Xiaoyun, (2019) believed that the New Retail Wheel Theory starts from four dimensions of retail namely; retail price, retail management level, technology and management, utility function and explores the

motivation and development direction of retail industry reform. The main principle of the theory is that, there are always companies that take the lead in technology. Those companies who take lead in technology always prosper. Those who lead in technological innovations usually attain high profits and trigger others to follow their footsteps (Briand & Richter, 2019). The companies who fail to adopt technological innovations are eliminated from the market. When other companies follow the technology of the leading companies the profit is shared and this result in low profits forcing the leading companies to innovate new technologies (Dixon et al, (2019). Thus, the theory further develops and enriches the retail cycle theory. The implications of the theory to the current study are that technology is the key to success for every modern company. Those companies that do not harness modern technologies and look forward for new technology remain behind of making their businesses grow (Hofmann, 2021).

Factors Promoting the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence by Retailers

There are a number of factors that promoted the adoption of artificial intelligence for automation by retailers in Zimbabwe. Some of the factors include; technological readiness, availability of big data, data quality, organisational culture, regulatory framework, cost and resource allocation, taxpayer acceptance, privacy and security concerns, skills and training and many others.

Technological Readiness

The present-day Zimbabwe and other countries in the global south have reached milestone in terms of acquiring high level of technology. In Zimbabwe high literacy rate enabled the country to be able to harness and implement high level of technologies (OECD, 2019). The availability of technological infrastructure is key for the development of AI. Technological readiness of the country enabled the country to be able to have AI intelligence being spread in all sectors of the economy including the large-scale retailers (Williams & Harris, 2020).

Availability of Big Data

The present modern world is characterised by the availability of big data in all sectors of the economy. In every large-scale retailer there is large amount of data received in every organisation (Islam & Karim, 2019). Big data refers to the large amount of raw, unorganised, and unprocessed facts and figures that are collected and stored in the organisation (Barnes & Owens, 2019). The availability of big data in every organisation demands high degree of accuracy. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enable the performance of data analytics to be easier (Goyal & Sigh, 2020). Human mind cannot be able to compute large amount of data. Thus, the need of AI as an effective tool to handle and process large amount of data accurately (Mishra & Singh, 2020).

Data Quality

Data quality refers to the degree to which data meets certain standards of accuracy, completeness, consistency, and reliability (Goyal & Sigh, 2020). Data quality is that data which suits well the intended purpose. High quality data is essential for valued decision making, research and business operations (Briand & Richter, 2019). The need for high quality data is relevant for effective informed decision making. Data quality has promoted the adoption and implementation of Artificial Intelligence in many contemporary organisations (Mishra & Singh, 2020).

Organisational Culture

Organisational culture is one of the major factors that promoted the adoption and implementation of AI in many modern organisations. The adoption and effective implementation of organisational culture in the context of AI refers to the shared values, practices and beliefs that shape how the organisation approaches artificial Intelligence (AI) adoption, development and deployment (David, 2019). Many organisations need to move with time as well as to be the part of the global village therefore, their organisational culture for adopting and effective implementation of AI in their business operations promote the use of AI

in every aspect of business activity (Ahmed & Mohamed, 2020).

Regulatory Framework

The term regulatory framework in relation to Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the set of laws, regulations, and guidelines that govern the development, deployment, and use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems (Carson, 2019). The regulatory framework aims to ensure that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is developed and used in a way that promote social good, minimise harm and protect human rights in accordance to the laws of the land (Burri, 2019, 2019). The adoption of the regulatory framework is also important in enabling the business organisation to adhere with the available ethics within the prevailing business environment (Weintraub, 2020).

Taxpayer Acceptance

The high level of willingness of the taxpayers to adopt Artificial Intelligence (AI) powered tax services promoted the adoption and effective implementation of modern technology by many nations (Daivid, 2019). In addition to that, the need to rich large number of taxpayers to accept and pay their tax burdens by the revenue authorities enabled the adoption and effective implementation of AI (Burri, 2019). Many large-scale retailers in the global south are now realising the significance of remitting their taxes to the revenue authority by harnessing the services of AI (Carson, 2019).

Privacy and Security Concerns

The need for Privacy and security concerns by many contemporary organisations promoted immensely the adoption and effective implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI). Privacy and security concerns in relation to AI refers to the potential risks and vulnerabilities associated with the collection, storage, and processing of personal data by AI systems (Dwork, 2019). The privacy and security concerns include; data privacy, data security, bias and discrimination, surveillance, accountability (Schneier, 2019). Data privacy and security is very important in every organisation in keeping confidential information of the organisation

(Crawford, 2019). Manual methods of safe keeping confidential information of the organisation is not effective than to protect data using Artificial Intelligence (Dwork, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence Applications in Retailing

There are a number of Artificial Intelligence applications in large retailing shops. Types of Artificial intelligence applications include; price optimization, fraud detection and prevention, predictive analytics for more accurate sales forecasting, supply chain optimisation, customer service chatbots and automated replies, inventory management, personalised recommendations and visual search and image recognition (Dixon et al, (2019).

Price Optimization

Price optimization AI application is adopted when analysing the market dynamics, competitor pricing and customer behaviour to dynamically adjust prices in retail stores. The adoption of price optimisation enables the retailers to optimize profits and remain competitive in the existing market (Dixon et al, 2019). Also, the revenue authority can be able to track the price optimisation of a retail shop for reconciling the tax filing.

Fraud Detection and Prevention

Fraud Detection and Prevention AI application is adopted by retailers in analysing transactional data and able to detect suspicious patterns indicative of fraudulent activities in the retail stores. Also, Fraud Detection and Prevention AI application enables the retailers to identify and mitigate fraud risks in real time (Collobert et al., 2021). The tax administrators too can be able to detect and mitigate tax evasion through real time and be able to protect themselves from tax losses. Retailers are also able to protect themselves from financial losses by keeping their customers safe in their establishments, safeguard customers information from various forms of scams (Siegel, 2021).

Predictive Analytics for More Accurate Sales Forecasting

Predictive Analytics for More Accurate Sales Forecasting AI is adopted for analysing the historical sales data, market trend and external factors to generate realistic and accurate sales (Kirizhevsky et al., 2021). In addition to that, Predictive Analytics for More Accurate Sales Forecasting AI is very important to retailers to anticipate demand fluctuations, able to optimise inventory levels and plan for effective marketing strategies that are relevant at a given place and time (Amaris et al., 2020). Also, revenue authorities are able to adopt Predictive Analytics for More Accurate Sales Forecasting such that they can be able to track all the sales made when reconciling with the actual sale written in the books of accounts (Dixon et al., 2019).

Supply Chain Optimisation

Supply Chain Optimisation AI is very important for analysing data from various sources of the business environment. Supply Chain Optimisation AI include, transportation routes, suppliers and demand forecasts (Amaris et al., 2020). Supply Chain Optimisation AI is also important in streamlining logistics processes, minimising disruptions and reducing lead time. Thus, Supply Chain Optimisation AI enables the retailers to reduce the operating costs (Collobert et al., 2021). Tax auditors can also harness the services of Supply Chain Optimisation AI to be able to track all the supplies made by the business and able to make the reconciliation between the actual sales revenue and the sales revenue presented in the books of accounts (Russell & Norvig, 2019).

Customer Service Chatbots and Automated Replies

Customer Service Chatbots and automated replies AI is very important to retailers as enabled retailers to engage with the customers in real-time, especially through the retail websites. Customer Service Chatbots and automated replies IA are also important to answer all the customers inquiries as well as to provide the product information and assist on purchasing of the products requested by the potential

customers (Poole, Mackworth & Goebel, 2021). Also, the tax auditors are able to inquire of the information relating to tax payments as well as to remind on taxes that are due to the client (Legg & Hutter, 2020). Customer Service Chatbots and automated replies AI are also very important in attracting many potential customers even if the retail shop does not have customers in place they can be accessible by many potential customers through virtual chatbots that are available 24/7. These chatbots are also important in enhancing customer service efficiently and satisfactorily while reducing operational costs available to the retailers (Bostrow, 2021).

Inventory Management

Inventory Management AI is a powered system that is used by retailers to forecast demand, automate replenishment and optimise inventory levels. Inventory Management AI enabled the retailers to accurately predict customer demand by offering specific products to the retailers at any given time (Russell & Norvig, 2021). Inventory Management AI also helps the retailers to avoid too much or too little stock that may lead to customer dissatisfaction. Inventory Management AI is also very instrumental especially to tax auditors in making the reconciliation with the stock that has been sold and the stock available for the business thereby able to compute the actual tax due based on realistic figures (Bostrom, 2021).

Personalised Recommendations

Personalised Recommendations AI is a machine learning used to analyse customer data, it also includes past purchase, preferences and browsing history of both new and existing customers (Bostrow, 2021). Personalised Recommendations, can also provide personalised product recommendations to potential customers. It helps retailers to raise sales by offering relevant products to each customer. Personalised Recommendations AI helps to maintain customer loyalty. Personalised Recommendations AI is also important for revenue authorities to be able to view all the business purchasing and compare it with sales when not satisfied by the accounting

information provided to them by the retailers (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

Visual Search and Image Recognition

Visual Search and Image Recognition AI is used by retailers to provide visual search capabilities in a digital platform or store. Visual Search and Image Recognition AI allow potential customers to search for products using images instead of using text (Goyal & Sigh, 2020). Thus, Visual Search and Image Recognition AI enable retailers to recognise technology as well as to enhance the search experience, provide a platform for a product discover, and discover, and drive conversations revenue, (Poole, Mackworth & Goebel, 2021).

Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Retail Operations Decision Making

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has both positive and negative effects on tax collection and decision making. Positive impact of Artificial Intelligence on retail operations and decision making include; improved accuracy, enhanced fraud detection, increased efficiency, better decision making, real-time monitoring, data-driven policy making, cost savings and many others (Birdi & Spencer, 2019).

Improved Accuracy

The adoption and implementation of artificial intelligence by retail shops enabled high degree of improved accuracy in computing retail accounting systems as well as to compute accurate taxes to be remitted to the revenue authority (OECD, 2019). Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms can analyse large datasets to enable the quick identification of existing errors, reducing manual mistakes and discrepancies (Carson, 2019). Retailers that adopt artificial intelligence in their business operations incurred less mistakes than the ones who are ignorant in adopting and implement artificial intelligence Walpole & Krever, (2020).

AI Enhanced Fraud Detection

The use of artificial intelligence by retailers enables fraud detection in performing business

activities. Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered systems can detect fraudulent activities, such as the identify theft and false claims, in real time (Burri, 2019). The revenue authorities are in a better position to use AI in detecting tax frauds or false claims on tax issues real time. By just clicking the button concerning the business transactions made withing a particular business operation the revenue authority personnel are able to detect tax frauds (Weintraub, 2020).

Increased Efficiency

Improved efficiency in business operations is enhanced by the adoption and effective implementation by the retailers. By adopting AI, the retailers are able to perform their business activities correctly without or with limited errors (Dwork, 2019). AI automates routine tasks, freeing resources for more complex and high value tasks. Also, the tax authorities are in a better position to come up with the actual amount of taxes that business organisation are able to pay at any given time and place (Burri, 2019).

Real Time Monitoring

The use of Artificial Intelligent is also important enable the real time tracking of all tax payments. AI enables tax authorities to identify delays or missing tax payments at any time (OECD, 2019). This facilitates responsibility by both taxpayers and tax collectors. AI is very important in enable the revenue authorities to be able to find out the missing tax payment and wrong tax payment just at the time in which the error has been made without delaying (Medeiros & Paulo, (2020). Thus, the tax is collected or to inform the taxpayer about the tax due before it loses its value (Crawford, 2019).

Data Driven Policy Making

Data-driven-policy making is made is by the adoption and effective implementation of artificial intelligence for the effective operations of the business organisations. AI is also important in providing insights for informed decision policy making (Burri, 2019). Organisations are in a better position to develop and effectively apply decisions that enables the effective attainment of the organisation

objectives. Tax authorities are also able to craft and implement decisions that are important to take the business organisation forward (OECD, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence Improve Customer Experience

The adoption of artificial intelligence by retailers enhances greater experience of the retail organisation with its potential customers. The development of e-commerce (electronic commerce) and the exponential growth of customer data have improved the efforts of retailers to identify the solutions for forecasting customer behaviour and improve customer experience. A study conducted by Maghraoui and Belghith, (2020) revealed that, data shared on the internet during the last decade exceeds those of the entire history of mankind. This was necessitated by the companies that owns, analyses, and utilised the data for their competitive advantages (Yang, 2020). In the retail sector technologies facilitate direct interactions between the company and the potential customers. Also, technologies allow for a better treatment of customer demands and their expectations (Collobert et al., 2021, Syan & Sharma, 2021). The retailers use chatbots to improve consumer experience by providing 24/7 services to both existing and new potential customers (Maghraoui & Belghith, 2020). Contemporary retailers are enjoying increasing popularity due to messaging services applications that enabled easy communication between the organisation and the customers. In the year 2022 H & M managed to be ahead of all Canadian large-scale retailers due to the application of chatbot which allow effective sharing, viewing and purchasing of the products (Bradlow, Gangwar, Kopalle & Voleti, 2020). One of the effective strategies retailers use robots in stores is to help customers to find the products they want at any given time and place. In the year 2019, the LoweBot robot of the retailer Lowe's was used in its stores in San Francisco (Bryson & Winfield, 2021). The customer's curiosity to view retail product through chatbots allows retail robots to become an essential lever in adopting a brand and

improve the consumer expectations (Capgemini, 2019).

Cost-Driven Savings

The adoption of AI enables the retailers to reach the targeted consumers with lower costs. Timing is important in retail by delivering the right message to the right potential customers at the right time (Lee & Shin, 2020). By applying big data technologies such as the predictive analytics, large scale retailers are able to predict the customer's buying behaviour hence they are able to make sound decisions for their current and future operations (Inman & Nikolova, 2021). The adoption of AI results in human workforce reduction due to the use of sensors, mobile this reduces the number of retail staff needed to work in a given retail shop. The use of smart shelves, photodetectors, encapsulating meshes of strain sensors, microphones and the spillage sensor to collect data on a product and send notification to the retail staff (David, 2019). Amazon's approach to AI stores involves Amazon Go app, which allows users to enter a physical store, buy products without scanning them manually, and they leave the shop without staying in a queue to stay (Ahmed & Mohamed, 2020). In a short explanation this process consists of three steps. Firstly, when entering the shop, the customer must register using the Amazon Go app from the smartphone. Secondly, when the product is picked by the customer from the shelves or put back the shelf sensors detect the move and the software updates the customer's virtual cart. Lastly when the customer leaves the store, a receipt is generated automatically at the same time Amazon account is charged. Thus, all these stages do not require any retail staff to be involved (Manasa & Jayanthila, 2022). Sensors, automation, robotics and artificial intelligence help to reduce staff costs generated from the warehouse to the retail shop.

Artificial Intelligence Enabled Revenue Growth

The adoption of artificial intelligence is also important in retail shops by enabling revenue growth of the retail business. Artificial intelligence technologies help retailers to

consolidate the sales strategy by leveraging existing stores features. AI enables price optimisation and sales optimisation and sales maximisation objectives (Briand & Richter, 2019). The use of big data technologies, detecting correlations between independent variables such as promoted price, display location, assortment expansions, and dependent variables like retail store sales and profitability, brand switching and many others (Anica-Popa et al., 2021).

Artificial Intelligence is Source of Competitive Advantage

The development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has brought a number of competitive age. Organisation that invests heavily in artificial intelligence growing faster than the organisations that are hesitant in adopting and implementing artificial intelligence are facing challenges and the majority of them are closing down (Manasa & Jayanthila, 2022). Large-scale retailers that adopted AI intelligence in their operations were performing well enjoyed large profits (Yang, 2020).

Challenges of Artificial Intelligence on Retail Performance and Decision Making

Despite a number of positive results that are enjoyed as a result of adopting and implementing decisions in an organisation. There are also, a number of challenges that are associated with the adoption of AI for tax collection and decision making (Dourado & Pestana, 2020). These challenges include; data quality issues, complexity of tax laws, lack of transparency and accountability, risk of bias, cyber risks, high implementation costs evolving nature of tax evasion (Mishra & Singh, 2020).

Data Quality Issues

The adoption and implementation of AI result in compromised data quality issues. It has been observed over time that the use of artificial intelligence in retail shops with incomplete data. All Artificial Intelligence algorithms require high quality data to produce accurate results (Islam &

Karim, 2019). However, most of the available tax data is found to be incomplete, inconsistent or sometimes outdated data is provided (Crawford, 2019). Wrong data is very dangerous as it results in misleading decision making that can cause harm to the operations and decision making of the organisations (Inman & Nikolova, 2020, Webster, 2022).

Lack of Transparency and Accountability

In many instances decision making in an organisation may be opaque, making it difficult to understand as well as to understand on how to make decisions (Weintraub, 2020). If the artificial intelligence is working with information that lacks transparency and accountability the result is poor decisions that may mislead the organisation operations (Ahmed & Mohamed, 2020).

Methodology

The study is guided by Pragmatism philosophy. Pragmatism philosophy was adopted by the study as it combines both qualitative and quantitative strategies in gathering and analysing data (Gray, 2018). The results of the study were objective and rich as a result of adopting pragmatism. Mixed research strategy was adopted by the research study to provide both numerical and detailed explanation of the results of the research study (Cresswell, 2019). The research design of the study is the correlational research design. Correlational research design was adopted to find the degree of relationship between artificial intelligence applications and the profitability of large-scale retailers (Burns and Burns, 2019).

Population of the Study

Population of the study is 119 potential research participants selected from five selected large-scale retailers in Gweru urban. The total population of 119 was established through the pilot survey conducted to establish the number of participants for the research study. Pilot study was very important for the study to establish the number of research participants, the number of large-scale retailers to be studied (Burns and

Burns, 2019). The research participants were drawn from the workers and management team involved, information technology, marketing, finance and various administrative activities.

Sample size of the research study

The study adopted Yamane (1967) sample size formula to reduce the total number of the population. The sample size of the study was arrived as follows:

The sample size of this study was determined using Yamane's Formula: 1967.

Yamane's formula:

$$n = N / [(1) + (N * e^2)] \quad (1)$$

Where: n = Sample Size

N = Target population

E = Level of significance/ marginal error 5%

Therefore, the target population of the study is 119

Substituting the target population on the Yamane's formula:

$$n = 119 / [(1) + (119 * 0.05^2)] = 92$$

Thus, 92 questionnaires were distributed to the research participants.

Sampling Techniques

The study adopted random sampling and convenience sampling to select research participants of the study. Random sampling was conducted by selecting research participants without following a well-defined order. Random sampling was simple and easy to use in selecting the research participants for the research study (Gray, 2018). Also, convenience sampling strategy was used to select research participants who were available at the time of research. Convenience sampling was important for the research study in administering the questionnaires through face-to-face interviews who were at the convenience of the researcher during the time of an interview (Cresswell, 2019).

Interviews for the Research Study

The interviews for the current research study were conducted through questionnaires and face to face interviews. Face to face interviews were limited to financial managers and marketing managers only. Financial managers were interviewed to provide the financial performance of large-scale retailers as a result of adopting artificial intelligence in the operations of large-scale retailers. Also, Marketing managers were selected to provide the changes in sales volume as a result of adopting and implementing artificial intelligence.

Response Rate

A total number of ninety-two(92) questionnaires were distributed to the research participants. Out of 92 questionnaires only five (5) of them were used to conduct face to face interviews with the finance and marketing managers selected from five selected large-scale retailers. Thus, 80 questionnaires were distributed to research participants to respond during the time of their convenience. This gives a total of 85 questionnaires that were successfully administered. This shows the response rate of 92.39 %. The response rate is above 75% thus, it is adequate to provide objective results (Sounders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2020).

Response Rate by Gender

The researcher succeeded in distributing 85 questionnaires to the potential research participants. A total of fifty-eight (58) questionnaires were administered to female participants, this constitutes a response rate of 63.04%. Also, a total of twenty-two (27) of the research participants were males this constitute a response rate of 29.35%. This shows that most of the employees in the large-scale retailers of Gweru urban were females during the time of research.

Diagnostic Tests

The diagnostic test was conducted through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The reliability test was performed measured by Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability test shows the result of 0.992. This shows that the instruments used for the

collecting data were reliable to give objective results. Table 2 shows the Reliability test.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.992	16

The Cronbach's Alpha of 0.992 for the 16 items indicates an exceptionally high level of internal

consistency, suggesting that the items are highly reliable and measure the same underlying construct.

Validity Tests

The validity of the research study was shown by performing autocorrelation test. Autocorrelation test was conducted to test on how validly were the instruments if they are continuously used on the extent of the reliability of the data.

Table 3. Model Summary for Autocorrelation Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.985 ^a	.970	.968	.22549	1.963
a. Predictors: (Constant), Visual search and Image recognition, Accurate sales forecasting, Price Optimization, Effective inventory management, Fraud Detection and prevention					
b. Dependent Variable: Profitability of large-scale retailers					

The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.963 suggests that there is no significant autocorrelation in the residuals of the regression model, indicating that the assumption of independence of errors is met.

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Price Optimization	.889	1.176
	Fraud Detection and prevention	.931	2.140
	Accurate sales forecasting	.727	2.411
	Effective inventory management	.873	1.631
	Visual search and Image recognition	.863	1.985
Dependent Variable: Performance of large-scale retailers			

The collinearity statistics indicate that there is no significant multicollinearity among the predictors in the model. The tolerance values, which range from 0.727 to 0.931, are all well above the threshold of 0.1, suggesting low multicollinearity. Correspondingly, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values, ranging from 1.176 to 2.411, are all below the commonly used cutoff of 10, further confirming the absence of

significant multicollinearity. These results indicate that the predictors—Price Optimization, Fraud Detection and Prevention, Accurate Sales Forecasting, Effective Inventory Management, and Visual Search and Image Recognition—can be reliably used in the regression model without concerns of multicollinearity affecting the stability and interpretability of the coefficients.

Table 5. Shapiro-Wilk test for Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Profitability of large-scale retailers	.174	80	.267	.908	80	.175
Price Optimization	.317	80	.178	.774	80	.325
Fraud Detection and prevention	.245	80	.463	.828	80	.216
Accurate sales forecasting	.397	80	.324	.712	80	.187
Effective inventory management	.312	80	.635	.828	80	.129
Visual search and Image recognition	.263	80	.243	.831	80	.421

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The Shapiro-Wilk test results for all variables Profitability of large-scale retailers ($p = 0.175$), Price Optimization ($p = 0.325$), Fraud Detection and Prevention ($p = 0.216$), Accurate Sales Forecasting ($p = 0.187$), Effective Inventory Management ($p = 0.129$), and Visual Search and Image Recognition ($p = 0.421$) indicate that the p -values are all greater than 0.05. This suggests that the null hypothesis of normality cannot be

rejected for any of these variables. Therefore, we can conclude that the data for each of these variables do not significantly deviate from a normal distribution, and the assumption of normality for these variables is met.

Impact of Artificial Intelligence Applications on the Profitability of Large-Scale Retailers

Table 6. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.977 ^a	.954	.954	.26986

a. Predictors: (Constant), Artificial Intelligence Applications

Table 7. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	118.839	1	118.839	1631.852	.000 ^b
	Residual	5.680	78	.073		
	Total	124.519	79			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability of large-scale retailers
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Artificial Intelligence Applications

Table 8. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-.383	.098		-3.889	.000	-.579	-.187
	Artificial Intelligence Applications	1.038	.026	.977	40.396	.000	.987	1.089

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of large-scale retailers

The regression analysis results indicate a very strong positive relationship between the of artificial intelligence (AI) application and the profitability of large-scale retailers, with an R

value of 0.977 and an R-squared value of 0.954. This suggests that 95.4% of the variability in retailer Profitability can be explained by AI applications. The ANOVA table shows a highly

significant F-value of 1631.852 ($p < 0.001$), confirming the model's overall significance. The coefficients table further highlights the substantial positive relationship of AI applications on the profitability of large-scale retailers, with an unstandardized coefficient of 1.038 ($p < 0.001$), meaning that for every unit increase in AI application, the Profitability of large-scale retailers increases by approximately 1.038 units. The narrow confidence intervals for the AI applications coefficient (0.987 to 1.089) reinforce the precision and reliability of this estimate.

Thematic Analysis

The study also conducted a face-to-face interview. The purpose of face-to-face interviews was to obtain in-depth views of the research respondents.

Theme 1: Importance of Artificial Intelligence

Question 1: How important is Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the profitability of your business?

Respondent 1:

The Artificial Intelligence (AI) has resulted in very high profits. Large profits obtained as a result of AI has managed us to expand our business to many parts of the country.

Respondent 2:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) was very important in our business as will managed to expand all our branches and we managed to increase the number of products we provide to our potential customers. Also, we managed to motivate our employees as a result of AI.

Respondent 3:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) contributed to the easy of doing business I our retail business. AI reduced significantly the costs of business operations. Also, AI resulted in very high profit margins and improved the going concern of our business which was about to fall before the adoption and effective implementation of AI.

Theme 2: Question two

Question 2: How do you intent to improve your Artificial Intelligence (AI)?

Respondent 4:

We are highly committed to keep on improving the development of AI in our all our business branches. Despite the fact that we have incurred high expenses and resistance in adopting and implementing AI in all our business branches the benefits are far more than the costs.

Respondent 5:

Our future is bright in the advent of Artificial Intelligence. We are looking forward to inject more financial resources into Artificial intelligence for the betterment of our business organisations. AI has transformed our business into the world first class retail business. We are not going to stop adopting and implementing new trends of Artificial Intelligence.

Theme 3: Importance of Artificial Intelligence

Question 3: How important is artificial Intelligence in decision making

Respondent 3:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is very important for decision making in the retail shops as it facilitates quick decisions the provide immediate online solution. Unlike the traditional system which was utilising critical decision making. The adoption of AI enabled the retail shops in making objective and valid decision than those who were made in the absence of Artificial intelligence.

Conclusion

The study adopted both quantitative and qualitative analysis of the study. Quantitative analysis was conducted through the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The qualitative analysis was conducted through face-to-face interviews guided by the thematic analysis. The results of the regression analysis show that, there is a positive significance between artificial intelligence applications and the profitability of the company. The more the

retail shops adopt and implement artificial intelligence the more the profit the organisation is making. On the other hand, the less the retail shops adopt and implement artificial intelligence the less the profit they make. Organisations need to adopt and implement optimal artificial intelligence that results in optimal profits. Retail shop need to understand the level of adopting and implementing artificial intelligence. Too much investment into artificial intelligence the less the profitability, this is because of the forces of diminishing returns. The failure by the retail organisations to adopt artificial intelligence results in the failure by the retail organisations to make significance profits.

Thematic analysis of the research study revealed that, artificial intelligence is very important for the performance of the business organisation. Effective business performance result in high profitability of the retail organisations. High profitability is of significance to enable business growth. The growth of the business organisations is important in high profits. High profits are a source of employee motivation. In addition to that, the adoption and implementation of artificial intelligence results in conveniences in conducting business activities.

The positive results enjoyed by retail shops as a result of adopting and implementing artificial intelligence motivated the local retailers to have a plan to adopt and implement more services of artificial intelligence. In addition to that, artificial intelligence is very important for decision making for retail shops. Retail shops that adopt and implement artificial intelligence are better in making effective decisions for the effective operations of the retail organisations.

Limitations and Future Research

The study revealed the significance of the adoption and implementation of artificial intelligence on the profitability of retail shops. The study add value to the existing academic body of knowledge the research was only limited to Gweru urban. There is need to conduct the same study in other large cities of the country. Also, there is need to adopt and implement the

study for artificial intelligence in other large retailers who are in various businesses such as clothing and hardware retailers. Future researchers are encouraged to research on the impact of artificial intelligence on the ethical issue surrounding the retail businesses. Future researchers to focus on the effects of artificial intelligence for automation on the effective collection of taxation. Also, future researchers need to focus on the role of the government in promoting artificial intelligence, and the challenges faced in adopting AI by large-scale retailers and the mitigatory measures in place to promote the effective adoption and use of artificial intelligence for automation in large-scale retailers for decision making.

Declaration by the Authors

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Author's Contribution

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Artificial Intelligence Applications Analysis

	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Uncertain		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Artificial Intelligence is very importance for the performance of Large-scale retailers	3	3.8%	2	2.5%	12	15.0%	12	15.0%	51	63.7%
Artificial Intelligence is very importance for the performance of Large-scale retailers	3	3.8%	2	2.5%	12	15.0%	12	15.0%	51	63.7%

	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Uncertain		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Technological Readiness	6	7.5%	11	13.8%	11	13.8%	8	10.0%	44	55.0%
Availability of big data	9	11.3%	11	13.8%	12	15.0%	10	12.5%	38	47.5%
Data Quality	6	7.5%	18	22.5%	18	22.5%	9	11.3%	29	36.3%
Organizational Culture	10	12.5%	24	30.0%	9	11.3%	6	7.5%	31	38.8%

	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Uncertain		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Price Optimization	5	6.3%	7	8.8%	17	21.3%	9	11.3%	42	52.5%
Fraud Detection and prevention	9	11.3%	11	13.8%	14	17.5%	13	16.3%	33	41.3%
Accurate sales forecasting	5	6.3%	4	5.0%	7	8.8%	53	66.3%	11	13.8%
Effective inventory management	8	10.0%	10	12.5%	15	18.8%	41	51.2%	6	7.5%
Visual search and Image recognition	7	8.8%	12	15.0%	23	28.7%	5	6.3%	33	41.3%

	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Uncertain		Agree		Strongly Agree	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Improved Accuracy	5	6.3%	6	7.5%	13	16.3%	43	53.8%	13	16.3%
Enhance fraud detection	9	11.3%	15	18.8%	16	20.0%	13	16.3%	27	33.8%
Real Time monitoring	12	15.0%	19	23.8%	17	21.3%	27	33.8%	5	6.3%
Data driven policy making	7	8.8%	7	8.8%	26	32.5%	9	11.3%	31	38.8%
Increasing company profitability	12	15.0%	15	18.8%	15	18.8%	7	8.8%	31	38.8%

Option 2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.985 ^a	.970	.968	.22549
a. Predictors: (Constant), Visual search and Image recognition, Accurate sales forecasting, Price Optimization, Effective inventory management, Fraud Detection and prevention				

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	120.757	5	24.151	474.979	.000 ^b
	Residual	3.763	74	.051		
	Total	124.519	79			
a. Dependent Variable: Performance of large-scale retailers						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Visual search and Image recognition, Accurate sales forecasting, Price Optimization, Effective inventory management, Fraud Detection and prevention						

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-.154	.108		-1.424	.159	-.369	.061
	Price Optimization	.226	.066	.233	3.442	.001	.095	.357
	Fraud Detection and prevention	.180	.101	.204	1.781	.079	-.021	.380
	Accurate sales forecasting	.101	.055	.078	1.832	.071	-.009	.210
	Effective inventory management	.017	.084	.015	.207	.837	-.150	.185
	Visual search and Image recognition	.443	.073	.488	6.045	.000	.297	.588
a. Dependent Variable: Performance of large-scale retailers								